

**PREPARATION OF WATER-INSOLUBLE FILMS BASED ON SILK
FIBROIN AND POLYSACCHARIDE.**

Sodiqova M.A.

Karimov A.

SHomurotov Sh.A.,

Institute of Bioorganic Chemistry of the Academy of
Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

e-mail; mohinursodiqova347@gmail.com (+998908249992)

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Complexity: it is possible to obtain compositions by connecting fibroin protein extracted from silkworms with various polysaccharides. From aqueous solutions of silk fibroin, films with varying parameters and characteristics are obtained. Thus, for example, nanoscale fibroin films can be obtained from aqueous solutions using the "layer-by-layer" technique..

This technique allows obtaining biopolymer coatings of the given size and thickness. Nano-sized films perfectly support the adhesion and proliferation of mesenchymal stem cells..

The aim of the study: It was shown that the growth and reproduction of fibroblasts in fibroin films is the same as in collagen films

. Other mammalian and insect cells have also been shown to adhere better to fibroin coatings compared to collagen films.

Chemically modified fibroin films improve cell attachment and bone formation. Methods and methods: fibrous materials made of polysaccharides and proteins are exposed to the natural environment of the body and thus provide favorable conditions for the growth and renewal of tissues. In this study, we obtained compositions based on fibroin-polysaccharide. Based on the above methods, a composite material in the form of film was obtained based on purified fibroin and dextran (dialdehydedextran). For this, a periodontal oxidation reaction with dextran was carried out, and dialdehyde products containing 10-90% oxidized links were obtained. It was determined that the molecular parameters of aldehyde dextran can be changed by changing the reaction conditions and the amount of aldehyde groups. The resulting dialdehyde products are reacted with primary amines to form azomethine-bonded compounds that are easily hydrolyzed. This allows them to be used as a polymer carrier in the preparation of long-acting macromolecular drug systems..

Results: Films prepared from aqueous solution of fibroin and dextran were obtained by casting. The fibroin and dextran solution was poured into Petri

dishes with a diameter of 35 mm. 50 μ m thick films were formed in Petri dishes. Films were dried at room temperature, then washed with ethanol and rehydrated with double distilled water.. To study the proliferative activity of cells, it is necessary to take into account the morphofunctional state of the product surface based on pure fibroin (fiber, matrix or hydrogel, depending on the material). Scanning electron microscopy and atomic force interference microscopy are often used as microscopy methods. One of the most universal parameters describing surface-cell adhesion is the value of the material's surface energy. Compared with other fibrillar proteins, an important feature of silk fibroin as a biomaterial is the versatility of sterilization options.

Conclusions: The film forming process was carried out as follows. An aqueous solution was prepared on the basis of fibroin and dialdehyde dextran separated by the above method. Their proportions were carried out in the proportions 1/1, 1/2, 1/3, 1/4, 1/5, and the concentration of the solution was 30 mg/ml. The solutions prepared in these proportions were poured into petri dishes and left to dry for 3 days at room temperature. Prepared films were washed twice with ethyl alcohol and removed from the Petri dish using a scalpel.

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